

A REVIEW ON JALAUKAVACHARAN IN VARICOSE VEINS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SIRAJ GRANTHI: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Varicose veins, these are permanently elongated, dilated vein /veins in tortuous way causing faulty circulation. It can also cause reversal of blood flow through faulty valves in veins. According to modern texts, risk factors of varicose veins includes prolonged standing, tight clothing, increased abdominal pressure, extensive muscular contractions ex. In rikshaw pullers, athlete's etc. It can occur in pregnancy were estrogen and progesterone levels are altered as well as in chronic smokers were there is deficiency of collagen levels in veins causing their tortuosity.^[1] According to ayurvedic texts varicose veins can be corelated with *Siraj granthi*, were symptoms of both are comparably same. In this case study, A 44 yr old Male patient with Bilateral tortuosity of veins and other related symptoms of varicose veins was treated successfully and found symptomatic relief with *Jalaukavacharan* along with Oral medication. In this paper we will discuss a review on *Jalaukavacharan* in Varicose veins with special reference to Siraj granthi in which *Raktamokshana* and *Raktaprasadan* will be the treatment of choice.

KEYWORDS: Varicose veins, Siraj granthi, *Jalaukavacharan*, Leech therapy, Tortuous veins, *Raktamokshan*.

INTRODUCTION

Varicose veins are referred to the condition in which the veins of lower limbs become dilated, tortuous, i.e. they appear swollen and bulged from outside. This are mostly seen in calf region, thigh and lesser extent in inner side of thigh. These are cause due to retrograde venous blood flow in lower limbs.

Varicose veins are mostly seen in people with long standing jobs which includes Policemen's, Housewife's, Rikshaw pullers, etc. These commonly includes symptoms such as night cramps, heaviness in leg's, pain, itching, etc. The pathophysiology of varicose veins includes Valvular incompetency which may be due to various causes. This can be divided into Primary and secondary causes.

Primary causes include loss of mural elastin and collagen, which leads to dilatation and separation of valve leaflets.

Secondary causes may be developmental weakness in the vein wall leading to secondary widening of venous valves resulting in secondary valvular incompetency.

Other causes of Varicose veins include muscle pump failure which is caused by chronic debility or immobility. VV are also commonly present in pregnancy.

According to Ayurvedic point of view the vitiated Vata and Rakta which localizes in limbs in polluted state causes squeezing and compression of veins over the limb's, which in turn produces Siraj granthi. The sign and symptoms of Siraj granthi resembles Varicose veins.^[2] So, the treatment of choice must include the

Vaathara chikitsa with Raktprasadan including the removal of stagnant vitiated blood. Jalaukavacharan removes the dushtakta and clears the pathway of doshas thereby removing Strotorodha. Also, Raktprasadan for dushtakta could be helpful.

Considering Ayurvedic literature Acharya Sushruta and Acharya Vagbhata mentioned Jalaukavacharan in all venous diseases which is a para-surgical procedure.

Clinical features of Siraj granthi are^[3]

- Sira Pratanam
- Sira sampidan
- Sira sankosh
- Sira Vishoshan

Clinical features of Varicose veins are^[4]

- Prominent, grossly dilated, tortuous veins over lower limbs
- Pain with cramps in calf region more during night
- Ankle swelling
- Eczema and pigmentation of affected limb
- Venous ulceration

As per above symptoms we can conclude that the symptoms of Siraj granthi has more resembles with Varicose veins.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sushruta Samhita

- 1) It has assigned two separate chapters for the description of the *Granthi*. According to Sushruta there are 5 types of *granthi* from which Siraj granthi is one of the types. In *Nidansthan* chapter no 11, *Samprapti* and *Nidan* of *granthi* are mentioned. In *chikitsasthan* chapter no 18 depicts the *chikitsa* of other *Granthi* 's but did not include *chikitsa* of *Siraj granthi*.
- 2) Acharya Sushruta described *Vataj Granthi* as resembles with swollen basti, and has clear bloody discharge.
- 3) *Pittaj granthi* shows sucking like pain, and has warm bloody discharge.
- 4) *Kaphaj granthi* is stony like (*pashanvat*) and has whitish discharge.
- 5) *Medoj granthi* increases its size with increase in body mass and decreases with the size and mass of the body.
- 6) According to acharya Sushruta, *Siraj granthi* is formed when a weak person does different types of exertional activities and so *kupit vayu* compresses and squeezes his all the group of veins and makes them dry, which in turn produces *granthi* in *siras* which is raised and circular. The swollen, bulging and twisted bluish veins that becomes visible just beneath the skin surface and filled with abnormal gathering of blood is known as *Siraj granthi*.

Charak Samhita

- 7) Acharya Charaka described 6 types of *Granthi*'s in Chapter no. 18 *Trishothiya Adhyay* of *Sutrasthana* and *Chikitsa* in chapter no. 12 *Shwayathuchikitsa adhyay* from which 5 are same as *Sushrutacharya* and 6th one is *Mamsaj granthi* which is caused due to habits of *Maamsdushtijanya aahar vihaar*.

Ashtang hrudayam

- 8) *Vagbhatacharya* told total 9 types of *granthi*'s in *Uttarstana* chapter no. 30. He included *Charaka*'s 6 types and added *Raktaj, Asthij, and Vranagranthi*.
- 9) *Acharya Vagbhata* described the cause of *Siraj granthi* is sudden diving in water.
- 10) *Vagbhatacharya* told *chikitsa* of *Siraj granthi* as *Sahachar tailpan, Upnah, Basti and Vyadhan* (Bloodletting).

Madhav nidana

According to *Madhav nidana granthi* is of 7 types *Vataj, Pittaj, Kaphaj, Raktaj, Mamsaj, Medoj and Siraj granthi*.

Historical milestones of Varicose veins

The origin of the word varicose comes from a Greek word 'Grapelike'. It was thought to be first used as a medical description by Hippocrates in 460BC. He advised the use of compression bandages and cauterisation to treat the condition.

AIM

To study the multidisciplinary approach in the clinical management of Siraj granthi with special reference to Varicose veins.

OBJECTIVE

To study the multidisciplinary approach in the clinical management of Siraj granthi based on Varicose veins.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Duration of study- 63days

Jalaukavacharan sittings - repeated on every 7th day

1-3 *Jalaukas* were applied to the patient over the effected extremity. The quantity of *Jalaukas* were decided as per the extent of severity of nodules and tortuosity of veins.

Total sittings done: - 9 (along with other Oral medications)

CASE REPORT

A 44yr old Male patient visited at Radhakisan Toshniwal Ayurvedic hospital, Akola. O.P.D no. 7 at Department of Shalyatantra, having complaints of Pain, heaviness, night cramps and severe itching on both the lower extremities from the past 12 years. He also had prominent dilated, tortuous veins covering both the lower limbs and discoloration of skin with multiple tiny pus pockets. According to the patient, the pain was more during standing and night hours with slight swelling on both the ankles. During physical examination ulceration was noticed.

RELEVANT HISTORY

N/H/O- HTN, DM, Thyroid or any other major illness
 N/H/O – Blood transfusion, allergy or any other Addictions

PAST HISTORY

The patient was apparently well until 12 years ago. Gradually, he began experiencing heaviness and nocturnal leg cramps. Over time, he developed pain and noticeable tortuous veins in the calf and inner thigh regions. Multiple pus pockets formed over the lower

extremities, causing severe itching and eventually progressing to ulcer formation. He underwent various treatment modalities, including allopathic, homeopathic, and even ayurvedic therapies at different hospitals. He also took *Shrung Chikitsa*, which provided only temporary relief. Each time he tried a new treatment, the relief lasted only for a short duration and the symptoms flared up more severely. As his symptoms failed to resolve permanently, he presented to our hospital for further management.

Table no. 1: Treatment schedule during the study.

SR.NO	TREATMENT	DOSE
1.	Raktamokshana by Jalauka (Leech therapy)	Every 7 th day
2.	Tab. Manjishtha Ghanvati	2 BD
3.	Tab. Kaishor guggulu	2 BD
4.	Tab. Guduchi Ghanvati	2 BD
5.	Shatdhaut Ghrita	Local application

RESULTS

The results showed promising symptomatic results in this patient. As per the study, the patient had good results in

pain management, skin discoloration, itching and redness.

Fig no. 3: After Treatment.**DISCUSSION**

Jalaukavacharana removes dushit Rakta and pacifies Vata–Pitta, improving circulation and reducing venous

stasis. As the stagnation of dushit rakt was relieved through Raktamokshana, eventually the signs of vitiated vaata and pitta dosha were comparably reduced after the

study These signs includes Pain, Night cramps, Itching and Skin discoloration. This study showed only mild relief on Tortuosity of veins that may be due to structural damage of veins that can't be reversed. Research showed leech therapy enhances microcirculation, prevents thrombosis, and accelerates healing. There are some bioactive components present in leech saliva such as hirudin, bdellins, eglins, and hyaluronidase.^[5] These actives provide anticoagulant, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic effects.^[6]

In support to this, some Oral formulations such as Tab. Manjishtha Ghanvati^[7], Tab. Kaishor Guggulu^[8], Tab. Guduchi Ghanvati^[9,10,11], and some other tablets for Raktashodhan were also dispensed to the patient. All these drugs are proven to have raktashodhak, raktaprasadak and vaatshamak properties. They also contain Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic properties which had helped in giving symptomatic relief to the patient in this study.

CONCLUSION

In this clinical trial, a single case was assessed systematically before and after treatment. Siraja Granthi is the condition observed more often in individuals engaged in prolonged standing work. So, Jalaukavacharana with oral herbal support provided to the patient, which showed marked relief in pain, itching, and skin discoloration, with mild improvement in night cramps, ankle oedema, and venous tortuosity. The therapy also helped to prevent secondary complications, it was cost effective and was well tolerated without any adverse effects. As per the observations, we can conclude that Jalaukavacharan can be useful in treating Varicose veins and its related symptoms.

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